

The Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument Survey Early Data Release *Is Available at the Astro Data Lab*

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The Early Data Release (EDR) of the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) survey comprises nearly two million spectra of galaxies, quasars, and stars obtained during the commissioning and survey validation phases of the observing campaign [1]. While DESI is designed primarily to be a world-leading cosmological experiment, the rich dataset from the EDR can enable a slew of scientific discoveries across a broader range of astrophysics.

The release of DESI data to the astronomical community is a major milestone in the ongoing tradition of collaboration between astronomy and particle physics, which has delivered great scientific benefits to both fields of research. The large sky surveys that are necessary to measure the signatures of dark energy also deliver massive samples of objects for astronomical data mining. NOIRLab facilities have been at the center of this mode of research from the original discovery of dark energy, to the Dark Energy Camera (DECam) and associated Dark Energy Survey, through DESI, and on to the Vera C. Rubin Observatory's forthcoming Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST).

The Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) making observations in the night sky on the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory in Arizona *Credit: KPNO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/T. Slovinsky*
The Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI)

dots) and quasars (red dots) in a small slice of the survey. The top wedge shows a high sampling with galaxies out to redshift 1.6 and distant quasars reaching redshifts 4–5, corresponding to light-travel time of 12 billion years. The bottom wedge zooms in to reveal more details of the large scale structures such as galaxy filaments, clusters, groups and interspersed voids. *Credit: E. Downing/DESI Collaboration*

Figure 2: (Top) Comparison of the [OII] 3726 & 3729 Å doublet in SDSS (L) and DESI EDR (R) spectra of the same galaxy

The DESI Collaboration has published a series of papers, including technical papers as well as a variety of scientific studies [2]. Given the vast applications, these works have barely scratched the surface, and much remains to be discovered. Of interest, some of the commonly studied extragalactic fields, such as the *Hubble Deep Field* and COSMOS, have been covered [3].

With its 5000 robotic fibers, and a nine-square-degree field of view, DESI is currently astronomy’s most powerful optical spectrograph. It can obtain up to 100,000 spectra in a single night of observing. This technological capability will enable the DESI Collaboration to reach its five-year goal of 40 million spectra of galaxies and quasars to create the largest-ever 3D map of the Universe [4]. The EDR gives us a glimpse of cosmic large-scale structures such as impressive galaxy filaments, clusters, and voids (Figure 1).

The DESI EDR includes catalogs of spectroscopic and photometric quantities as well as fully processed, flux-calibrated, and extracted spectra from the automated pipeline run at the National Energy Research Computing Center (NERSC). Each spectrum comes with a best-fit template model and redshift measurement. The public data release at NERSC comprises primarily serving files. To augment this, the [Astro Data Lab](#) at the Community Science and Data Center (CSDC), a program of NSF’s NOIRLab, hosts a searchable `desi_edr` catalog database for efficient data discovery and retrieval. The database is accessible via methods such as a web query interface, Table Access Protocol (TAP) handle for tools such as TOPCAT, or a Jupyter notebook server [5]. In addition, the DESI spectra themselves

can be obtained through CSDC’s new [Spectra Analysis and Retrievable Catalog Lab \(SPARCL\)](#). To facilitate data exploration, the Astro Data Lab team has developed several [tutorial Jupyter notebooks](#) in collaboration with the DESI team [6].

One example notebook demonstrates how to search a region of the sky for available spectra from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) DR16 [7] and from the DESI EDR and how to use a value-added catalog with emission-line measurements to select an interesting galaxy with copious ionized gas traced by an Oxygen transition ([OII] doublet at 3726 & 3729 Angstroms). The notebook then shows how to combine Astro Data Lab databases together with the SPARCL spectrum-access service to quickly retrieve spectra of interest in a fraction of a second. Finally, zooming in on the spectra around the Oxygen lines highlights that the spectral resolution of DESI is sufficient to resolve the doublet (Figure 2). This capability is key to the DESI experiment, as it allows easy differentiation of [OII] from single emission lines in a large number of faint emission-line galaxies (ELGs), which are used as cosmological tracers of the underlying distribution of matter in the Universe.

made with an [example Jupyter notebook](#) available on the Astro Data Lab platform [4]. DESI’s comparatively higher spectral resolution is key to splitting the doublet components, allowing [OII] to be used to obtain accurate redshift measurements. (Bottom) Images from the [Legacy Surveys Sky Viewer](#) of the SDSS layer and LS DR9 layer used for DESI targeting. *Credit: R. Pucha/University of Arizona, NOIRLab/AURA/NSF/S. Juneau, NOIRLab/AURA/NSF/Astro Data Lab team*

installed on the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory near Tucson, Arizona. Credit: NOIRLab/KPNO/NSF/AURA/P. Marenfeld

Figure 1: Early DESI data showing the distribution of galaxies in the universe.

The DESI Collaboration continues to grow its dataset, having obtained spectra of over 26 million galaxies, quasars, and stars thus far. Within this context, the early release of 2 million spectra might seem like only the tip of the cosmic iceberg, but it also represents a treasure trove of data available for exploration. The astronomy community is invited to [join in](#) this exploration as discoveries await to be made.

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Kitt Peak National Observatory is a program of NSF's NOIRLab. The DESI collaboration is honored to be permitted to conduct scientific research on Iolkam Du'ag (Kitt Peak), a mountain with particular significance to the Tohono O'odham Nation.

References

- [1] DESI Collaboration et al. 2023a, arXiv:2306.06307
- [2] DESI technical papers. <https://data.desi.lbl.gov/doc/papers/>

- [3] DESI Collaboration et al. 2023b, arXiv:2306.06308
- [4] DESI Collaboration et al. 2016, arXiv:1611.00036
- [5] Nikutta, R. et al. 2020, A&C, 33, 100441
- [6] Juneau, S. et al. 2021, CiSE, 23, 15
- [7] Ahumada, R. et al. 2020, ApJS, 249, 3

Useful Links

SPARCL: <https://astrosparecl.datalab.noirlab.edu>
Astro Data Lab: <https://datalab.noirlab.edu>
DESI Landing page: <https://datalab.noirlab.edu/desi>

Tutorial Jupyter Notebooks

Introduction to DESI EDR notebook

https://github.com/astro-datalab/notebooks-latest/blob/master/03_ScienceExamples/DESI/01_Intro_to_DESI_EDR.ipynb

How to use the SPARCL notebook

https://github.com/astro-datalab/notebooks-latest/blob/master/04_HowTos/SPARCL/How_to_use_SPARCL.ipynb

SDSS vs. DESI EDR Comparison notebook

https://github.com/astro-datalab/notebooks-latest/blob/master/03_ScienceExamples/DESI/02_DESI_EDR_SDSS_Comparison.ipynb

How to query the desi_edr database notebook

https://github.com/astro-datalab/notebooks-latest/blob/master/04_HowTos/QueryClient/How_to_query_DESI_EDR_Data.ipynb